

Table 1. Statistical parameters computed for Henderson's equation.^a

Temperature (°C)	R ^e	SE ₂	p	s
<i>Rough rice</i>				
20 (adsorption)	0.9979	0.0237	4.9641	0.4095
20 (desorption)	0.9948	0.0331	5.7493	0.4783
30 (adsorption)	0.9977	0.0250	5.2291	0.3010
30 (desorption)	0.9977	0.0251	5.2715	0.2357
40 (adsorption)	0.9899	0.0558	7.6946	0.8303
40 (desorption)	0.9953	0.0352	5.9828	0.5682
<i>Brown rice</i>				
20 (adsorption)	0.9994	0.0093	3.1245	0.1305
20 (desorption)	0.9960	0.0251	5.2788	0.3315
30 (adsorption)	0.9859	0.0508	7.8132	0.5572
30 (desorption)	0.9776	0.0598	8.5309	0.7026
40 (adsorption)	0.9900	0.0454	6.8859	0.7269
40 (desorption)	0.9902	0.0427	6.6738	0.6718
<i>3.8% milled</i>				
20 (adsorption)	0.9972	0.0235	5.0352	0.3737
20 (desorption)	0.9998	0.0050	2.4068	0.0850
30 (adsorption)	0.9968	0.0255	5.5695	0.3177
30 (desorption)	0.9970	0.0228	5.4673	0.3104
40 (adsorption)	0.9991	0.0131	3.8546	0.2079
40 (desorption)	0.9979	0.0198	4.7039	0.3077
<i>6.6% milled</i>				
20 (adsorption)	0.9996	0.0081	3.0446	0.1335
20 (desorption)	0.9923	0.0338	5.7109	0.4279
30 (adsorption)	0.9877	0.0549	7.4310	0.9935
30 (desorption)	0.9835	0.0552	7.6346	0.9665
40 (adsorption)	0.9958	0.0320	5.8086	0.4939
40 (desorption)	0.9952	0.0294	5.5697	0.4641
<i>10.3% milled</i>				
20 (adsorption)	0.9892	0.0429	6.9858	0.4655
20 (desorption)	0.9817	0.0497	7.5638	0.6273
30 (adsorption)	0.9819	0.0645	9.1193	0.7998
30 (desorption)	0.9752	0.0637	8.6034	0.8722
40 (adsorption)	0.9851	0.0622	7.6785	0.6956
40 (desorption)	0.9973	0.0221	5.7347	1.0400

^aR^e = coefficient of determination, SE₂ = standard error, p = mean relative percentage deviation, and s = root mean square deviation.

Table 2. Statistical parameters computed for GAB's equation.^a

Temperature (°C)	R ^e	SE ₂	p	s
<i>Rough rice</i>				
20 (adsorption)	0.9936	0.0006	3.9883	0.2612
20 (desorption)	0.9990	0.0003	2.9043	0.1165
30 (adsorption)	0.9936	0.0008	4.7826	0.2228
30 (desorption)	0.9984	0.0003	3.5050	0.1175
40 (adsorption)	0.9885	0.0009	4.3692	0.3356
40 (desorption)	0.9917	0.0008	4.7374	0.3099
<i>Brown rice</i>				
20 (adsorption)	0.9980	0.0004	3.6122	0.1939
20 (desorption)	0.9978	0.0004	3.9362	0.2375
30 (adsorption)	0.9972	0.0006	4.5757	0.2252
30 (desorption)	0.9952	0.0008	5.4132	0.3315
40 (adsorption)	0.9971	0.0005	3.9738	0.2139
40 (desorption)	0.9988	0.0003	3.4296	0.1473
<i>3.8% milled</i>				
20 (adsorption)	0.9986	0.0003	3.2353	0.1382
20 (desorption)	0.9989	0.0003	3.3169	0.1758
30 (adsorption)	0.9953	0.0007	4.6853	0.2709
30 (desorption)	0.9963	0.0006	4.6299	0.2771
40 (adsorption)	0.9995	0.0002	2.3235	0.0840
40 (desorption)	0.9977	0.0004	3.1643	0.2108
<i>6.6% milled</i>				
20 (adsorption)	0.9975	0.0004	3.8472	0.2250
20 (desorption)	0.9963	0.0006	4.9695	0.3102
30 (adsorption)	0.9938	0.0007	4.3361	0.2854
30 (desorption)	0.9998	0.0003	2.9866	0.1748
40 (adsorption)	0.9997	0.0004	3.4870	0.1818
40 (desorption)	0.9977	0.0004	2.5486	0.0908
<i>10.3% milled</i>				
20 (adsorption)	0.9961	0.0007	5.1185	0.2481
20 (desorption)	0.9976	0.0005	4.8273	0.2713
30 (adsorption)	0.9940	0.0008	4.8769	0.2995
30 (desorption)	0.9934	0.0008	5.6662	0.4186
40 (adsorption)	0.9889	0.0009	5.4052	0.3466
40 (desorption)	0.9977	0.0004	8.1920	0.9818

Partitioning of high-density grains and its implication in a rice selection program

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One approach to break the yield barrier in irrigated rice yields is to increase the number of high-density (HD) grains panicle⁻¹. Previous work reveals that yield potential can be raised by 30% with more HD grains panicle⁻¹. HD grains are fully filled grains with a specific gravity of 1.20 and above. Grain filling is generally superior in primary branches compared with secondary branches in the panicle. Therefore, HD

grains panicle⁻¹(HDGP) must be partitioned into its components: number of primary branches (PB) panicle⁻¹, number of secondary branches (SB) panicle⁻¹, number of HD grains on primary branches (HDGPB), number of HD grains on secondary branches (HDGSB), HD grain index on primary branches (HDIPB), HD grain index on secondary branches (HDISB), and HD grain index panicle⁻¹

(HDIP). These traits should be related to the end product, grain yield panicle⁻¹ (GYP).

We studied the components of HD grains in five short-duration rice varieties in an experiment conducted during 1997 kharif in a randomized block design with five replications. Twenty-five-day-old seedlings of each variety were planted in a 5 × 4-m² plot and at a spacing of 15 × 10 cm.

At maturity, 25 random panicles of the main tillers in each variety in each replication were selected for HD grains and their component characters. HD grains were separated by soaking the grains in salt solution with a specific gravity of 1.20. The HD grain index was calculated as a ratio of the number of HD grains to the number of spikelets and expressed in %.

The highest values for GYP, HDGP, and HDIP were noted in KAU-MO-1-80 (see table). TKM 9, which had relatively higher

HDGP and HDIP, had lower GYP because of lesser grain weight. MO 7 and MO 8, which had lesser HDIP, had higher GYP because of more HDGP. In general, HDISB was lower than HDIPB; this was more pronounced in varieties MO 7, MO 8, and MO 9, which had lower HDIP. These results revealed that HDIP, which was mostly decided by HDISB and HDGPB, could be increased by higher HDGSB. Thus, the possibility of enhancing yield potential exists in MO 7, MO 8, and MO 9.

A wider variation was noted for secondary branches as well as HDGSB than for primary branches and HDGPB. GYP was strongly and positively correlated with HDGP, secondary branches, and HDGSB. In turn, HDGP had a strong positive correlation with HDGSB and secondary branches. The study suggests that to increase the number of HD grains panicle⁻¹ (and thereby yield level), plants with more secondary branches panicle⁻¹ and more HD grains on these branches should be selected.

High-density (HD) grain and its component characters in five rice varieties, 1997 kharif, Karaikal, India.

Character ^a	MO 7	MO 8	MO 9	KAU-MO-1-80	TKM 9	Mean	CD (5%)	r ^b with HDGP	r with GYP
PB	11.90	12.05	10.70	11.80	8.45	10.98	0.89	0.28	0.62**
SB	23.75	31.90	19.15	33.40	22.80	26.20	5.63	0.77**	0.87**
HDGPB	53.38	51.80	47.85	66.65	50.40	54.02	7.08	0.64**	0.77**
HDGSB	48.15	64.85	27.55	81.65	61.15	56.67	10.22	0.98**	0.84**
HDIPB	80.35	74.23	73.40	92.53	88.90	81.88	8.48	0.58**	0.32**
HDISB	65.45	54.25	46.05	81.05	86.17	66.60	10.35	0.64**	0.32
HDIP	72.20	62.05	60.05	88.83	86.20	73.86	10.32	0.62**	0.28
HDGP	101.53	116.65	75.40	148.30	111.55	110.68	14.35	-0.87**	
GYP	3.34	3.53	2.24	3.86	2.71	3.13	0.22	--	

^aPB = number of primary branches panicle⁻¹, SB = number of secondary branches panicle⁻¹, HDGPB = number of HD grains on PB, HDGSB = number of HD grains on SB, HDIPB = HD grain index on PB, HDISB = HD grain index on SB, HDIP = HD grain index panicle⁻¹, HDGP = HD grains panicle⁻¹, and GYP = grain yield panicle⁻¹.
^br = simple correlation coefficient. **Significant at P = 0.01.

KDML 105, an alternative aromatic rice for the semideepwater ecosystem

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About 77% of ricelands in Assam are annually submerged for 2-10 d or more due to rain and flood in the wet season. The predominant winter rice (Sali) is often inundated from 50 to 200 cm, resulting in extensive damage to the crop. The semideepwater rice grown in the lower regions can tolerate submergence, but the yield and cooking qualities of the kernels are lower than those of Mahsuri. Mahsuri is a popular winter rice. Joha, a group of wet-season rice varieties grown on upland

to medium land, which cannot withstand submergence, is well-known for its strong aroma, superfine grain, and excellent cooking quality. But Joha's productivity is only 2-3 t ha⁻¹.

We introduced KDML 105, a native, aromatic semideepwater rice of Thailand, in Assam during 1995 from an international germplasm exchange program of IRRI. KDML stands for "Khao Dawk Mali" in Thai, meaning Jasmine white kernel. KDML 105 can withstand 50-80 cm submergence,

stands erect until maturity, flowers by the end of October, and can be grown as direct-seeded semideepwater rice or as wet-season winter rice in Assam.

Table 1 shows the yields of KDML 105 from 1995 to 1997 over 14 locations in five districts of Assam. KDML 105 had a pooled average mean yield of 4.2 t ha⁻¹ over years and locations, with 33% more yield than local semideepwater variety Panikekoa, and 51% more than the best Joha variety—Kolajoha.